

MODELS OF PROBLEM SOLVING IN MANAGEMENT PROCESSES

N.Mavlonov

Associate Professor of the Institute of International
School of Finance Technology and Science (PhD)
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ANNOTATION

Two main models of problem solving in the management process: The first model is the bureaucracy model presented in the book of the German sociologist Max Weber. This model is based on a set of rules necessary for making all decisions. These rules are universal and do not correspond to any real situation. Therefore, the bureaucracy does not have a public character. In his evaluations, a person attaches importance to individuality and individual characteristics. When faced with bureaucracy, he strives for a concrete decision. However, sometimes applicable rules and requirements impose decision options that do not take features into account.

Key words: *particular disease, personalization model, patient's condition, general methodology, concrete situation;*

The main model is the decision personalization model. It is possible to do something similar to the example of a doctor treating him. Based on the symptoms characteristic of a particular disease, the doctor analyzes the patient's condition, makes a diagnosis and makes a decision. Since there are no two exactly the same patients, the indices are also different. There is only a general methodology for solving problems based on the knowledge and experience of the doctor. For example, a surgical operation is always unique.

Management cannot be completely governed by bureaucratic rules. Likewise, administrative decisions should not be bureaucratic. They are a product of the manager's professionalism and his ability to deal with concrete situations.

Types of decisions

In a bureaucratic system, management decisions are based on rules. In such conditions, many decisions at the levels of the administrative system are fairly standard and unchanging. When there are rules that justify the manager's decision, they reduce his decision-making responsibility and do not require a searching approach to understanding the problem.

Such decisions are sometimes called programmatic or model (typovoy). They are accepted according to the instructions, they will definitely have a certain share in the manager's activity.

A manager is influenced by the external and internal environment when developing a management decision. The external environment is customers, competitors, political and general social conditions. Internal environment - company's organizational environment, personnel, technology. Also, the opportunity to grow one's career, the interaction of important factors determines the choice of decision.

Decision making process

Decision making is a complex process. The main task here is to explain the problem.

But for this, it is necessary to correctly assess the situation, i.e., the existing conditions, and clearly work towards the goal. In some cases, the symptoms of a problem are unclear due to the lack of knowledge of its causes. The manager needs to study all the symptoms, and for this it is necessary to know the situation well and compare it with the goal. No problem can be solved until its root cause is identified. For example, if a manager has problems with employees who do not show up for work or who are always late, then this symptom will have negative consequences for the causes of lateness. Perhaps the employee has transportation difficulties or some other reasons; therefore, before dismissing him for being late, it is necessary to find out the reason.

Determining the nature of the problem is a difficult process. Before making a final decision, it is necessary to try to identify the causes of the problems. After determining the cause of the problem and understanding its content, the next step is to determine the solutions that can solve the problem. Best of all, express your opinion in writing. to act There are often multiple solutions to the same problem. As they are written down and evaluated, the specific advantages and disadvantages of each solution option become apparent. Only when you compare the solution options will you find the rational and logical one among them.

In sorting out possible solutions, each option should have certain outcomes that can be measured in some evaluation system. The manager should try to predict the results of the decision he made. Solutions whose consequences cannot be determined cannot be supported. When choosing and evaluating solutions, consider the goals and how the solutions will help them achieve their goals. The manager is responsible for the quality of the solution.

The next step is organizational-practical activity on manifesting solutions. This is also a complicated process. The solution may create a certain conflict that the staff is unfamiliar with. In most cases, to announce solutions to some problems to employees, do not rush. Ideally, this should be done in conjunction with employee feedback as a gradual implementation process. A general rule of thumb for a manager is "caution" Apart from that, there is no set of rules about how to approach the problem of applying solutions. Solutions come faster and better when employees are involved in creating them, rather than being imposed on them from above. is used.

The next step is to control the implementation of decisions and the results. It is not always possible to predict the outcome of the decisions made. Only controlling the decision-making process shows what they are worth. Previously, the words "Leader" (guide) and "upravlyayushiy" (Manager) were often used. To better understand the decision-making process of leaders and managers, it is necessary to distinguish them from each other.

difference between the tasks of the team leader and the head of the department comes from the difference between the tasks of the leader and the manager.

The leader conducts management on the basis of personal decision-making and control over the work process. The leader does not take away the right to make decisions, but on the contrary, he transfers this right to each member of the brigade or team. Its main purpose is not to make decisions, but to find problems that other members of the team need to solve, and to provide assistance in forming the goals and tasks of the team. Accordingly, the task of controlling the labor process (that is, ruling over employees based on administrative coercion) is replaced by the task of reconciliation, that is, the search for ways to reconcile the various, often conflicting, interests of employees.

in the decision-making process or, in other words, in the management style, are based

primarily on the specific aspects of the relations between people today and the objective needs of development .

A factory worker at Frito Lay in California, a real example of the organizational culture and new management thinking in the US, said , " We attack problems, not people. We attack 'who 's wrong . ' " We will decide what needs to be done , not just what to do," he said. A separate meeting room was set aside for solving such issues , where employees of various departments meet regularly to discuss their problems.

The preparation and decision- making process can be divided into 5 steps :

- 1) to systematically analyze the educational process or other types of activity and identify conflicts and inconsistencies that cause problems in time ;
- 2) additional data for analysis and forecasting ;
- 3) maybe work options ab chi q work ;
- 4) of the solution determine the efficiency expected when implementing individual options ;
- 5) choosing the best solution.

General decisions do not exist in isolation from each other. They often form a chain aimed at achieving a certain goal.

The general decision is one of the main documents that highlight the appropriate improvement measures taken by the leader .

can be considered in the preparation and implementation of decisions :

- this way, it is better to increase the scientific basis of decisions and reduce the risk of taking risks ;
- what should be the amount of information needed to prepare the decision ;
- how to coordinate the activity of interested persons in the process of preparing the decision .

it is necessary to act in three directions :

- of the general decision , use of the best calculation methods and accounting techniques ;
- creation of a system of practical control over the implementation of the adopted decisions ;
- decision -making process, i.e. involving as many people as possible in its implementation .

Employee incentive system _

have accumulated a great deal of experience in motivating their employees .

But each era relies on its own methods. In our time, the methods of encouraging the initiative of workers are recommended to the attention of leaders. Here are some of them :

1. Become an entrepreneur. Constantly look for new forms of labor organization, strive to strengthen creative cooperation among employees .
2. Focus on the aspects of organizational culture that stifle and limit initiative .
3. an environment of freedom of communication and openness so that your employees can share information and ideas with each other and with you .
4. Explore and consider the personality traits of your employees. Appreciate the abilities of each.

5. Ensure that those who complete the initiative are rewarded more than before .

6. Try to assign tasks to your employees that are personally and professionally rewarding when completed .

7. Instill in everyone that success achieved with passion can only be laughed at by employees who are creatively active .

8. not punish too much . Often , the severity of the punishment is several times higher than the size of the assessment . Also , a person who has fallen once can lose confidence in his own abilities . If possible , appreciate the achievements and try not to notice the shortcomings .

9. Take advantage of criticism constructively , gradually, even if it is limited to a limited area . Talk to friendly and kind people .

The above ten tips are just a few of the things managers need to know . But after getting to know them, his psychology, su h batdosh got a job . it begins to become clear that the knowledge of science and other similar fields should be deepened .

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